

The low-altitude economy in Uzbekistan: Unlocking growth across water, agriculture and energy

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KEY MESSAGES:

- **Uzbekistan's drone reform opens a new economic policy window.** The 2026 decision to reopen civil drone use can become the foundation for a low-altitude economy that supports productivity, infrastructure monitoring and digital services
- **Uzbekistan's drone reform opens a new economic policy window.** The 2026 decision to reopen civil drone use can become the foundation for a low-altitude economy that supports productivity, infrastructure monitoring and digital public services.
- **The main value of drones lies beyond aviation.** For Uzbekistan, drones are most relevant not as a transport innovation alone, but as a practical tool for agriculture, water management and energy infrastructure.
- **Water, agriculture and energy should shape the new framework.** These sectors face urgent productivity, climate and infrastructure challenges, and drone technologies can improve monitoring, reduce costs and support faster operational decisions.
- **The legal framework should not be designed as an aviation-only reform.** If the reform focuses mainly on transport and security, it may miss the needs of the ministries, utilities, farmers and infrastructure operators that will use drones at scale.
- **Public demand can help create the market.** Government agencies, donor-financed irrigation projects and energy companies can become early customers, helping set standards for safety, data use, certification and service quality.

- **Uzbekistan can position itself as a regional drone-services hub.** Early action on regulation, training, certification and data systems would allow the country to shape Central Asian standards for drone use in water, agriculture and energy.

1. Introduction

In February 2026, Uzbekistan adopted Presidential Decree UP-22, which creates a policy path for liberalising civil drone use by legal entities after more than a decade of restrictive regulation. By June 2026, four government bodies are expected to prepare the draft legal framework that will turn this policy direction into an operational regime. This brief argues that the reform should not be treated only as a transport and security issue. It can become a foundational decision for three sectors that will shape Uzbekistan’s development over the next decade: water management, agriculture and the energy transition.

The brief explains what the “low-altitude economy” means in practical policy terms. It shows how drones, small unmanned aircraft and the digital systems that manage them can generate concrete gains across water, agriculture and energy. It also identifies the main risks of a poorly designed rollout and proposes a sequenced set of actions for the first phase of implementation.

2. What is the “low-altitude economy”?

The “low-altitude economy” (LAE) refers to commercial and public-service activities that take place in low-altitude airspace, usually below about 1,000 metres above the ground and, in some cases, up to 3,000 metres in designated corridors. China, where the term first entered national policy, uses it to cover drone delivery, agricultural drones, inspection of pipelines and power lines, small electric passenger aircraft (Electric Vertical Take-off and Landing, eVTOLs), low-altitude tourism, and the digital and physical infrastructure required to manage these activities (APCO Worldwide, 2025; Wang and Xing, 2025; Jamestown Foundation, 2026).

The low-altitude economy has three main components:

- The aircraft themselves: small, medium and large drones, as well as battery-powered passenger aircraft.
- The services they provide: crop spraying, remote sensing, infrastructure inspection, border monitoring, parcel delivery, passenger mobility and emergency response.
- The enabling systems: unmanned traffic management (UTM), landing pads, charging stations, designated flight corridors, digital maps and connectivity infrastructure.

The Civil Aviation Administration of China (CAAC) projects that China’s low-altitude economy will reach RMB 1.5 trillion, or about USD 211 billion, in 2025 and exceed RMB 3.5 trillion by 2035 (Xinhua, 2025). Uzbekistan does not need to copy China’s model. Its geography, economic structure and regulatory starting point are different. However, the basic categories of the LAE are now sufficiently clear to inform Uzbekistan’s own policy design.

3. Why this matters for water, agriculture and energy in Uzbekistan

Three sectoral facts shape the policy case.

Water is the country's most important economic risk. By 2050, Uzbekistan is projected to face an annual water shortage of 11-13 cubic kilometres, roughly five times the current gap (ADB, 2022). The glaciers that feed the Amu Darya and Syr Darya river systems are shrinking rapidly, increasing pressure on regional water security (UNESCAP, 2025). Land degradation in the Aral Sea basin and dust emissions from the dried seabed also create direct risks for agriculture, public health and livelihoods in Karakalpakstan (World Bank, 2024a).

Agriculture remains central to employment, rural incomes and export potential. It generates around 17-19% of GDP and about one quarter of employment, depending on the source and year used (World Bank Open Data, 2024; U.S. International Trade Administration, 2025). At the same time, water productivity remains low. World Bank reviews have highlighted major losses in irrigation systems, including leakage and obsolete pumping infrastructure, which reduce the amount of water that reaches farms – [up to 70% in some places](#) (World Bank, 2019).

Energy infrastructure is expanding at an unprecedented speed. By the end of 2026, Uzbekistan plans to add 6.7 GW of new power capacity, including 2.8 GW of solar, 470 MW of wind, 884 MW of energy storage, as well as new thermal and hydropower capacity (Enerdata, 2026; UzDaily, 2026). By 2030, the government aims to reach more than 20 GW of solar and wind capacity and a substantially higher renewable-energy share in the power mix (UzDaily, 2025). New nuclear and green-hydrogen projects, including the Jizzakh nuclear power plant and the Chirchiq green-hydrogen complex, will add further demand for high-quality monitoring, inspection and safety systems (ACWA Power, 2023; Ammonia Energy Association, 2023; World Nuclear News, 2025; 2026).

These three sectors are closely connected. Irrigation pumping is a major source of summer electricity demand, while upstream water releases in Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan shape both downstream irrigation availability and regional hydropower generation (OECD, 2022b; Clingendael, 2025; World Bank, 2024b). This is the water-energy-food nexus. For Uzbekistan, drone technology is one practical tool that can support decision-making across all three parts of this nexus

4. The February 2026 Presidential Decree

On 18 February 2026, media reports on the implementation of Presidential Decree UP-22 stated that four bodies - the Ministry of Defense, the Ministry of Transport, the Ministry of Digital Technologies and the Agency for Strategic Development and Reforms - were tasked with preparing, by June 2026, a draft framework to liberalise drone imports, production and use by legal entities (Kun.uz, 2026). The emerging framework is expected to introduce:

- Permission for legal entities to import, manufacture and operate drones, subject to licensing;
- A “green-yellow-red” zoning system indicating where drones may fly freely, conditionally or not at all;
- A national digital flight-management system, linked to the existing “atm safe sky” platform, with qr-code registration of flights;

- Standards for pilot training and certification, including rules for beyond-visual-line-of-sight operations where needed.

The main institutional gap is that the three ministries likely to become the largest end users - Agriculture, Water Resources and Energy - are not listed among the co-leading agencies. The Ministry of Agriculture has already moved ahead. By 2025, it operated a drone service centre with more than 100 agricultural drones. In 2026, it expected 50 additional drones from China and mobile drone teams in each region. In March 2026, it signed a memorandum with Kaizen Aerospace and the State Scientific-Design Institute “O’zdayerloyiha” for drone operations across up to 300,000 hectares of cotton (Kun.uz, 2025; DroneLife, 2026). If pursued strategically and with broader stakeholder engagement, the low-altitude economy could become an important instrument for productivity growth and infrastructure resilience in Uzbekistan.

Table 1. Potential applications of drones across agriculture, water management and energy in Uzbekistan

What the drone does	Agriculture	Water	Energy
Spraying crops from the air	Cotton, wheat, fruit and vegetables	Not a primary use case	Not a primary use case
Cameras that pick up heat, water stress and plant health	Yields, salinity, water stress, pests	Salinity in irrigation areas	Faulty solar panels, overheating equipment
Inspecting long stretches of infrastructure (visual, heat, laser)	Not a primary use case	Canals, drains, pumping stations	Power lines, distribution networks
Heat-camera survey of solar farms	Not a primary use case	Not a primary use case	Hot spots, dust build-up, micro-cracks
Inspecting wind-turbine blades and towers	Not a primary use case	Not a primary use case	Bash, Kungrad, Navoiy wind farms
Surveying dams, intakes and spillways	Not a primary use case	Reservoirs, dams, spillways	Hydropower facilities
Long-distance deliveries	Seeds, vaccines, lab samples	Water-quality samples	Not a primary use case
Mapping dust storms and tracking tree planting	Not a primary use case	Aral Sea bed restoration	Not a primary use case
Surveying glaciers and snowpack	Not a primary use case	Snowpack and glacier extent	Hydropower planning
Cameras that detect gas leaks	Not a primary use case	Not a primary use case	Hydrogen and ammonia leak detection
Watching the nuclear plant site	Not a primary use case	Not a primary use case	Jizzakh nuclear power plant

5. What the LAE can deliver

5.1 Agriculture

Drone spraying can reduce water and chemical use. Independent research reviews indicate that drone spraying can significantly reduce water and chemical inputs compared with tractor-based spraying, while maintaining or improving treatment effectiveness (Guebsi et al., 2024; Rejeb et al., 2022). The Ministry of Agriculture's March 2026 memorandum with Kaizen Aerospace targets up to 300,000 hectares of cotton. Combined with more than 100 drones already in service, this creates a practical basis for national rules on safe spraying, residue testing and pilot certification, as well as for the development of a domestic drone-services industry (Kun.uz, 2025; DroneLife, 2026).

Drones can identify crop stress earlier and more precisely. Multispectral and thermal cameras can detect water stress, plant health problems and pest risks at plot level. Studies in the Fergana Valley show that irrigation scheduling based on crop needs can save 25-34% of water without reducing cotton yields (Mukhamedjanov et al., 2017; Conrad et al., 2013). Drones can complement satellite data by providing higher-resolution information, especially where field conditions vary sharply over short distances (Ma et al., 2022).

Drones can support selected rural logistics services. In East Africa, regular drone deliveries have reduced delivery times for medicines and laboratory samples to remote clinics by 70-90% (Access Health International, 2025). In Uzbekistan, carefully regulated routes in Karakalpakstan, Surkhandarya and Namangan could support delivery of seeds, veterinary inputs, vaccines and laboratory samples in areas where road access is costly or slow.

5.2 Water

Drones can improve inspection of canals, drains and pumping stations. Drones equipped with visual and thermal cameras are increasingly used to inspect long stretches of infrastructure (DJI Enterprise, 2024; UAV Coach, 2026). This is directly relevant for Uzbekistan, where major international programmes are investing in irrigation modernisation, including EBRD, World Bank and ADB-supported projects (EBRD, 2025; Interfax, 2025; Kun.uz, 2022; UzDaily, 2025). Making drone inspection a standard element of these projects, and later integrating it into the routine work of basin water organisations and Water Users' Associations, would help translate the new legal framework into measurable water-management gains.

Drones can strengthen monitoring of the dried Aral Sea bed. The dried bed of the Aral Sea, known as the Aralkum, is a major source of salty dust storms. The UNDP "Green Aral Sea" initiative and the World Bank's landscape-restoration work both highlight the need for regular monitoring of afforestation and land-restoration activities (UNDP, 2025; World Bank, 2024a). Drone imagery can help identify dust-source areas, monitor the survival of saxaul plantings and guide future restoration work.

Drones can support regional glacier and snowpack monitoring. The ADB-led Green Climate Fund "Glaciers to Farms" programme and UNESCAP's work on melting glaciers point to a clear opportunity for Uzbekistan and neighbouring countries to share drone-based monitoring data and feed it into regional water-information systems (UNESCAP, 2025; UzDaily, 2025).

5.3 Energy

Drones can reduce the cost of solar-farm inspection. Thermal drones can detect faulty panels, dust build-up, micro-cracks and broken cells faster than manual ground inspection (DJI Enterprise, 2024). As Uzbekistan scales solar and battery projects, regular drone inspection can support asset performance, warranty compliance and insurance requirements across large utility-scale projects (ACWA Power, 2023; Astana Times, 2025; Enerdata, 2026; PV Magazine, 2026; Renewables Now, 2024).

Drones can make wind-turbine inspection safer and faster. ACWA Power's Bash and Kungrad wind projects, together with other planned wind investments, will require regular inspection of towers, blades and related infrastructure (ACWA Power, 2023; Astana Times, 2025; Enerdata, 2023). Drone-based inspection can reduce safety risks for workers and shorten downtime compared with conventional inspection methods.

Drones can support grid modernisation. ACWA Power alone is developing about 1,450 km of transmission lines, while the wider electricity-distribution system requires major investment to reduce technical losses and integrate new renewable generation (ACWA Power, 2023; World Bank, 2025). Drone inspection can help identify electrical discharge, broken wires, faulty insulators and vegetation risks along transmission and distribution corridors.

Drones can improve hydropower and dam inspection. Drones can inspect dams, water intakes, spillways and gates more safely and frequently than many ground-based methods. This is particularly relevant for regional cooperation on water and power with Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan (OECD, 2022b; Clingendael, 2025).

Drones can support construction monitoring at sensitive energy sites. The Jizzakh nuclear power project will require strict monitoring of construction progress, site security and environmental baselines (World Nuclear News 2025; 2026). Any drone use around such facilities should remain subject to national security rules and relevant international safety standards.

Drones can support monitoring of hydrogen and ammonia facilities. ACWA Power's green-hydrogen project in Chirchiq is planned around an initial annual production capacity of 3,000 tonnes, with longer-term links to green ammonia production (ACWA Power, 2023; Ammonia Energy Association, 2023). Specialised drones can help monitor pipelines, tanks and industrial sites from a safe distance, provided that their use is integrated into facility safety protocols.

6. Implementation risks and mitigation measures

A poorly designed rollout could raise costs, weaken public trust and limit the productivity gains expected from the reform. The main risks specific to a water-, agriculture- and energy-focused drone strategy are summarised below.

Three risks require particular attention: chemical drift in agriculture, data systems that do not feed into decisions, and security around critical energy sites. Each can be managed through clear standards, institutional responsibility and targeted safeguards.

Table 2. Key risks in developing a water-agriculture-energy-focused drone economy and possible mitigation measures

#	Risks	What it looks like in practice	What to do about it
1	Spray drift and chemical residue on food	Drone spraying can drift in the wind, leaving chemical traces that hurt sales of fruit and vegetables to the EU and Gulf	Set common rules for safe spraying; test residues regularly; license pilots (drawing on FAO guidance and the European drone regulator EASA's model)
2	Data without operational use	Drone images of salinity or dust storms sit in folders because no one is responsible for acting on them	Make sure Water Users' Associations and basin offices use the data; publish open data with a 1-2 month delay
3	Security around critical sites	Drones could be misused near the nuclear plant, hydrogen plants and high-voltage power lines	Anti-drone defences at sensitive sites; only registered, trained operators; rules aligned with International Atomic Energy Agency standards
4	Uneven regional access	Drone services are easiest to deliver to large agribusinesses near Tashkent and to big private power developers, leaving Karakalpakstan and other low-income areas behind	Subsidies for "drone services for smallholders"; explicit Karakalpakstan-priority and women's-participation targets
5	Not enough trained people	Pilots, inspectors and air-traffic managers in short supply	New training programmes at agricultural and technical universities and vocational colleges; target 5,000 certified pilots by 2030
6	Single-supplier dependence	Agriculture, Water and Energy are not co-authors of the new law, even though they will be the biggest users	Add them as formal co-authors of the June 2026 legislation
7	Too much reliance on one country's drones	Most drones available are Chinese; if supply or trade is disrupted, services stop	Source drones from a mix of Chinese, Turkish, Korean and European suppliers
8	Privacy and noise complaints	Surveys consistently find that ordinary people worry about drones spying on them and making noise	Clear rules on what data drones can collect and store; quieter aircraft standards (Sun et al. 2025)

7. Uzbekistan and its neighbours

Central Asian countries face similar climate, water and infrastructure pressures, but they start from different positions. Uzbekistan has a large domestic market and a fast-growing combination of water and energy infrastructure to manage. Kazakhstan has moved earlier in drone manufacturing. Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan hold much of the region's water and hydropower potential, but have more limited domestic drone capacity. Turkmenistan remains more closed, with less public information available.

Table 3. Central Asian comparison of sectoral conditions and low-altitude economy signals

Country	Agriculture (% GDP / jobs)	Water pressure	Energy direction	Drone / LAE signal
Uzbekistan	~17-19% / ~24% (World Bank Open Data 2024)	90% of water in agriculture; 11-13 km ³ shortfall by 2050 (ADB, 2022)	Rapid expansion of solar, wind and storage capacity; nuclear and green-hydrogen projects under development (Enerdata 2026; UzDaily, 2025; Renewables Now, 2024; World Nuclear News, 2025; 2026)	February 2026 decree opens the market; 100+ farm drones already in service; 50 more from China; Kaizen MoU; Sahro Drone manufacturing
Kazakhstan	~5% / ~13% (World Bank Open Data)	2024 wheat harvest down 26% in heatwave; depends on Syr Darya and Ili rivers shared with neighbours (Caspian Policy Center, 2025)	Largest oil and coal economy in the region; growing wind and solar; nuclear referendum approved (Atlantic Council, 2025)	Yesil Technology USD 12m drone manufacturing centre; Polyking USD 200m industrial park (~1,500 jobs) (Parks 2025)
Tajikistan	~22% / ~45%	About 60% of the region's water originates here; trade-offs between hydropower and irrigation; fruit losses in 2025 heatwave (UNESCAP, 2025)	80-90% hydropower; Rogun dam under construction (Clingendael, 2025)	Limited domestic drone capacity; pilot demand for inspecting mountain hydropower and irrigation
Kyrgyzstan	~12% / ~20%	Glacier-fed; pasture degradation in Naryn and around Issyk-Kul (UNDP, 2023)	80-90% hydropower; new wind pilots (Clingendael, 2025)	Drone use still early; growing donor interest in glacier monitoring
Turkmenistan	~10% / ~25% (estimated)	Heavy cotton focus; piloting drip irrigation and drought-resistant varieties (Times of Central Asia, 2024)	Gas-dominated; very limited renewables (OECD, 2022a)	Limited public information; closed regulatory environment

The country that combines a workable licensing regime with steady public demand for drone services will be well placed to shape regional standards for pilot training, data, certification and after-sales support. For Uzbekistan, the opportunity to move first is strongest over the next 24 months.

8. The way forward

A drone law that includes the right sectoral institutions

The June 2026 draft framework should involve the Ministries of Agriculture, Water Resources and Energy alongside the four bodies named in the February decree. These ministries are likely to become the largest end users of drone services, and their absence from the drafting process could produce a transport-and-security framework that under-serves the country's most pressing economic needs. The legal text should include three elements: clear rules on safe spraying, residue testing and pilot certification; a defined pathway for beyond-visual-line-of-sight flights for irrigation and energy infrastructure; and security rules around the Jizzakh nuclear power plant, the Chirchiq hydrogen complex and high-voltage transmission corridors. Aligning the national framework with risk-based international approaches, including the European Union's open, specific and certified flight categories, would help Uzbek operators work with an interoperable standard from the start.

Public demand as market creation

The fastest way to convert the law into measurable productivity gains is to use public demand as an early market signal. The Ministry of Agriculture, the State Committee for Geodesy, basin water organisations and the National Electric Grid could issue framework contracts for crop spraying, multispectral monitoring, inspection of donor-financed irrigation infrastructure, inspection of solar and wind farms, transmission lines and battery sites, and leak detection at hydrogen-related facilities. Donor-financed infrastructure projects could also include drone inspection as a standard monitoring requirement. Sourcing should be diversified across Chinese, Turkish, Korean and European suppliers to reduce single-supplier exposure. Data collected by drones on salinity, water stress and asset condition should feed directly into Water Users' Associations, basin offices and grid-operator planning cycles, with public release after an appropriate delay where security and privacy conditions allow.

Skills, infrastructure and equity, starting with vulnerable regions

Without trained people and shared infrastructure, even a well-drafted law will produce limited results. Drone training tracks could be opened at agricultural, technical and IT-oriented universities, as well as selected vocational colleges, with a target of 5,000 certified pilots by 2030 and a clear target for women's participation. The national drone-traffic system based on "ATM Safe Sky" should be expanded with operator access, visible no-fly zones and integration with traditional air traffic. Beyond-visual-line-of-sight corridors, regional drone service centres and shared maintenance hubs should be linked to existing extension offices, machinery rings and energy-company depots. Karakalpakstan and other climate-vulnerable regions should be prioritised to prevent the market from concentrating only around large agribusinesses and private energy developers.

A regional platform for drone services and data

Uzbekistan's potential market extends across Central Asia. Mutual recognition of pilot licences, drone certification and data-sharing standards through regional platforms would allow qualified operators to work across borders and position Uzbekistan as a hub for regional drone services. Two initiatives could be launched in parallel: a regional drone-based glacier and dust-storm monitoring network linked to the Aral Sea agenda, and an inspection-data exchange among regional power companies in support of the Central Asian Power System. Both would generate practical evidence of what the new framework can deliver and could help set standards that neighbouring countries would adopt.

9. Conclusion

The 2026 reform turns a long-standing restriction into a real economic opportunity. Whether this opportunity produces measurable gains for farmers, water users and electricity consumers will depend on how the new framework is designed and implemented. If it is treated mainly as a transport and security file, the reform may remain narrow. If it is linked to water, agriculture and energy strategies, it can support productivity, infrastructure resilience and regional competitiveness. Involving the relevant sector ministries, using public demand to create the market, building shared infrastructure, turning data into operational decisions and training enough specialists would align the reform with Uzbekistan's broader priorities in productivity, irrigation modernisation, private-sector development and energy transition. The period between the June 2026 draft framework and the first operational year of implementation will determine whether Uzbekistan becomes an early regional leader in the low-altitude economy.

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